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Research paper

Trend and inequality analysis of operational land holdings in Bareilly District, Uttar Pradesh

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Abstract

Land is a very important resource for all human communities. In rural area where mostly of the people depend on land for their livelihood, it plays a strategic role in the determination of the economic, social and cultural progress. However, the land is limited and there is increasing competition for its use. Small and medium farmers dominate Indian agriculture which is characterised by the incidence of tendency, landlessness and a high degree of fragmentation which directly affect their economic condition. The ownership of land and its distribution pattern directly affects the distribution, accumulation and generation of wealth in rural areas. Therefore, much work has been done to study land holdings in terms of distribution and distributional inequalities. In this research work an attempt has been made to analyse the various aspects of operational land holding in the Bareilly district comparing the year 1991 to 2016 from the geographical point of view. This study is based on secondary data sources where various statistical and geospatial techniques have been used to analyse the data. Thus, this paper provides an insight into the spatio-temporal distribution and pattern of operational land holdings in the Bareilly district and their changes in terms of number and area.

Keywords: Agriculture, Landholdings, Inequality, Bareilly.

Introduction

Land and its uses are important to all human communities. It is particularly important for rural communities where many people depend on land for their livelihood. Land resources play a strategic role in the determination of the economic, social and cultural progress of a region. However, the land is limited and there is increasing competition for its use. Small and medium farmers dominate Indian agriculture, characterised by the incidence of tendency, landlessness

and a high degree of fragmentation which directly affect the agricultural production and income (Sharma, 1994). The ownership of land and its distribution pattern directly affects the distribution, accumulation and generation of wealth in rural areas. Due to rapid population growth the pressure of the population on land is increasing and Indian agriculture is undergoing heavy stress as the average land holding is decreasing day by day (Poornia, 2015). According to the annual report of NABARD 2013-14, the acreage of land has remained at 140 million hectares for 40 years but the number of farmers has increased from 7 crores to 14 crores. We are adding one crore farmers every five years. Due to the lack of other occupations in rural areas, people started to put much pressure on agriculture which is a major reason for the continuous fragmentation of land.

Land has been important aspect from which people avail food, home and income which affects their livelihood. The ratio of the people who depended directly on the land has been smaller in number but the number of people who depend on agriculture in rural areas of the country still growing rapidly. The equality in distribution of land could create a sustained growth and development for the society which will act as a stepping stone to build a developed nation (Binswanger, et al.). Deininger (2003) and Easterly (2007) analysed in their research that only two of the 15 developing countries with unequal land distribution managed to grow their economies at more than 2.5% over the period 1960–1992 (Deininger and Squire, 1998). Sokoloff and Engerman had compared North and South America continents in which they have found that the large land holdings were the basis for political inequalities which were used to block investment to improve education for the majority of the people. The secured and equally distributed land rights had helped to improve the people socially and economically which contributed as a democratic, peaceful, productive and gender equality among the people in the developing nations. The improvement in service centers and agricultural support services with positive effects could bring changes as far as health and education services are concerned (Lipton and Saghai, 2017; Deininger, 2003; Lipton, 2009; Prosterman and Riedinger, 1987). The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) which was adopted in 2015, included targets and indicators related to land inequality (SDG indicators 1.4.2, 5.a.1. and 5.a.2).

Changes in the global and national economies are bringing new pressures that people responded in different ways of changing their land uses, livelihood strategies and lifestyles in rural areas in what some describe as “new rurality” (Ramirez-Miranda, 2014; Hecht, 2010). For many people, the land is bound up with their spiritual and cultural lives and sense of identity. Some argued that far from seeing land as a commodity for us to own we should see ourselves as belonging to the land and being responsible for its wellbeing (Black, 2011). Whether directly linked to land or not the land is vital for all of us and future generations as a common good that we depend on for essentials such as clean air, water and biodiversity.

Despite the agricultural change, we can see that the marginal and small farmers have not been benefited as compared to other farmers in the study area. On the other hand, most large farm holders are receiving the benefits due to the advantage of purchasing power and other reasons regarding social, cultural and political influences. So we can see that with average land holding size, the cost of getting inputs and time consumed has doubled. If these are not tackled now, it will be challenging to maintain agriculture as a feasible profession. The institutions such

as the World Bank and International Monetary Fund (IMF) now propagate the view that land redistribution to landless, marginal and small farmers would lead to much overall productivity. As a result, there are declining trends observed in the size of agricultural holdings in the past. In future, the fragmentation of land holdings is likely to continue and the average size of land holdings is expected to decrease further in the study area. To make small holdings more viable and increase farm incomes, the Government has taken several measures including adopting modern technologies and practices like multiple cropping, intercropping and integrated farming systems. Now a day, only agriculture on a small piece of land is not enough to live an average life for a farmer in India. In order fill this gap the present study aims at analysing the trends, blockwise change and the level of inequality in operational land holdings in the study area.

Methodology

This study is primarily based on secondary data sources. The data of the decadal change from 1991 to 2016 has been collected from the District Statistical Handbook of Bareilly District, Primary Census Abstract, several literature including books, articles and published as well as non-published materials. The development blocks have been considered as the basic unit of the study. The data has been analysed in Microsoft excel. The analysis and interpretation have been done through textual and tabular formats followed by the result and discussions. Arc GIS software has been used for mapping purposes. The Gini coefficient has been computed to study the variation in operational land holding and area distribution for the year 1991 and 2016. The following Gini coefficient formula is used for this purpose.

Gini Coefficient formula

$$G_i = 1/10000 (\sum X_i Y_{i+1} - \sum X_{i+1} Y_i)$$

Where X_i and Y_i refer to the cumulative percentage of holding and area operated respectively by the i^{th} group. The value of the Gini coefficient ranges from '0' (perfect equality) to '1' (perfect inequality).

Study area

Bareilly district is located in the northwestern part of U.P. and lies between latitudes 28°01' to 28°54' North and longitude 78°58' to 79°47' East. Bareilly district has an area of 4,120 sq. km. Bareilly District is bounded by Uttarakhand state on the North, Rampur District on the West, Badaun District on the South and Pilibhit District on the East. Its maximum length from North to South is about 96 Km and its breadth from east to west is about 75 Km. The district has been divided into six tehsils. It is also divided into fifteen development blocks i.e. Baheri, Bhadpura, Bhuta, Bithrichainpur, Faridpur, Fatehganj west, Alampur Jafraabad, Kyara, Majhgwan, Meerganj, Nawabganj, Ramnagar, Richha and Shergarh, respectively. Bareilly district is well connected by Railways and Roadways. National Highway 24, state highway 33 and many metaled roads make connectivity easier through the district.

Ramganga is the main river of the district and Bahgul, Shankh, Devrania, Nakatia and Kailasi are some other rivers flowing in the district. According to the 2011 census, the district has 31 towns and 2051 villages. Out of 44, 48,359 persons in the district, 64.7 percent (2,879,950) live in rural areas and 35.3 percent (1,568,409) in urban areas. Bareilly has a sex ratio of 887 females for every 1000 males. The average literacy rate in Bareilly district, as per the census of

India, 2011, is 58.49%, where male and female literacy is 67.50% and 48.30%, respectively. The population of the district depends heavily on agriculture to earn their livelihood. Land-related inequality is a central component of the wider inequality that is one of the burning issues of our society today. It affects us all and directly determines the quality of life for billions of people who depend on land and related resources for their livelihoods. The district Bareilly has its headquarter at Bareilly city. The district has been marked as one of the backward district by the government of Uttar Pradesh. The Bareilly city has been selected as the smart city for its holistic development by the government of Uttar Pradesh.

Figure 1: Location map of the study area

Result and Discussion

Changes in operational land holdings

Agriculture is the primary occupation of most of the population in the study area. The district's population depends heavily on agriculture to earn their livelihood. Land-related inequality is a central component of the wider inequality that is one of the burning issues of our society today. It affects us all and directly determines the quality of life for billions of people who depend on land and related resources for their livelihoods. Figure 2, shows the unequal land distribution

among different landholding categories. There have been a significant change in the total number and area of land holdings in the Bareilly district from 1991 to 2016 observed. 77.37 percent of the total farmers have less than 1 hectare of agricultural land while 15 percent have 1-2 hectares of agricultural land. The proportion of semi-medium and medium landholders are 6.12 percent and 1.40 percent respectively; the percentage of large landholders is only 0.09 percent in the study area.

Figure 2, shows the unequal land distribution among different landholding categories in 1991 and 2016. There has been a significant change in the total number and area of land holdings in the Bareilly district during this time period. Figure 2, indicates that the percentage of small (-3.07percent), semi-medium (-3.32 percent), medium (-1.40 percent) and large (-0.09 percent) land holdings is decreased whereas the marginal land holdings have increased from 1991 to 2016. When we talk about the changes in area during this period, we can see a maximum increase in area under the marginal landholding (15.13 percent) because the number of marginal farmers is increased. At the same time, the area under small (-0.17 percent), semi-medium (-6.77 percent), medium (-6.95 percent) and large landholding (-1.24 percent) categories have decreased. Maximum decreased in area occurred in medium landholding. The main reason behind decreasing size of land holdings among the farmers are rapidly increasing population and land fragmentation due to division in the family.

Figure 2: Changes in the number and area of operational land holdings (1991-2016)

Figure 2, shows a positive growth in number and area of marginal land holdings whereas small, semi-medium, medium and large classes registered a negative growth in both number and area. This clearly indicated towards the unequal land distribution in study area, the data

showed that the area under marginal size class has increased but it has increased marginally. The decreased area under agriculture, decrease in large size holdings and fragmentation of farmland are the factors responsible for not performing well for the agricultural sectors. This is one of the reasons, why GDP is not growing at the expected rate because agricultural sector is not contributing to the GDP.

Block-wise change in operational land holdings

Land fragmentation is commonly used to refer to the process of land holdings getting smaller and to the phenomena of one farmer's land holding being made up of several smaller parcels of land that are not necessarily contiguous nor evenly shaped. Figure 3 shows the block-wise changes during the census year 1991 to 2016. It can be observed that the maximum development blocks recorded a positive change in the number and area of operational landholdings. During this time period the area under operational land holdings has increased in all the development blocks. There have been decreased operational landholdings in three development blocks namely, Bhadpura, Nawabganj and Alampur Jafarabad.

Figure 3: Changes in operational land holding and operated area (1991-2016)

Faridpur block (0.65 %) recorded the maximum change while the lowest change was seen in the Bhadpura block (-1.18 %) in operational land holding. Bhadpura block (1.46 %) recorded the highest positive change whereas Majhgawan block (-6.36 %) recorded the lowest change in operated area. The shift of the economy from primary to the secondary and tertiary sectors, sacrificing agricultural land for urbanization, to reside the growing population and industrial development are the major reasons for the change in operation landholdings. The people are also giving up agriculture to look for a better lifestyle or maybe there are a lot of landless farmers. Further, the farm size keeps getting smaller and smaller causing a reduction in

the agricultural productivity. Fragmentation of farmland is a common practice in Indian society due to inheritance but it also fragmenting the agricultural economy.

Inequality in operational land oldings

It is observed that the value of the Gini coefficient was 0.018 in 1991 and further it has decreased to 0.003 in 2016 which shows that the inequality over the years have been decreasing. Though it has been decreasing it still persists in the in the study area. It can be regulated by governing authorities with proper targeting to the problems specific to a particular region or social group. The Gini value of 0.018 shows high inequality among the large and marginal landholders and the area operated by them because maximum marginal farmers have less land as compared to large landholders. Most of the time, maximum and small farmers mainly depend on agriculture. Hence, land fragmentation happened more in the marginal landholders than the larger landholders in which they operated the land. In addition, the population of the marginal landholder's family increases more than the larger landholder's family, creating a huge gap between the landholding and the area operated by them as compared to large farmers because they are also engaged in secondary and tertiary works for their livelihood. So, their land is not divided as compared to marginal and small farmers.

Table 1: Cumulative percentage of operational holdings and area (1991-2016)

Blocks	1991				2016			
	Cumulative % of Operational holding (Xi)	Cumulative % of Operated area (Yi)	$X_i Y_{i+1}$	$X_{i+1} Y_i$	Cumulative % of Operational holding (Xi)	Cumulative % of Operated area (Yi)	$X_i Y_{i+1}$	$X_{i+1} Y_i$
Baheri	10.54	10.46	174.88	171.81	10.46	10.49	170.96	172.89
Shergarh	16.43	16.59	367.07	360.74	16.48	16.34	357.18	357.67
Richha	21.74	22.34	596.11	593.35	21.89	21.68	579.62	581.35
Meerganj	26.56	27.42	861.98	859.97	26.82	26.48	837.16	841.09
Fatehganj west	31.36	32.45	1181.87	1179.72	31.77	31.22	1148.88	1151.22
Bhojipura	36.35	37.69	1551.44	1546.75	36.88	36.16	1509.49	1506.25
Kyara	41.04	42.68	1957.55	1947.43	41.65	40.93	1902.28	1894.70
Ramnagar	45.63	47.69	2471.09	2442.41	46.29	45.67	2384.28	2391.29
Majhgawan	51.21	54.16	3121.08	3182.14	52.36	51.51	3088.87	3073.03
Alampur	58.76	60.95	3979.54	3987.79	59.66	59.00	3914.83	3925.43
Jafrabad	65.43	67.73	4890.71	4995.42	66.54	65.62	4917.00	4838.76
Bithri-chainpur	73.76	74.75	5972.70	6095.85	73.74	73.90	6017.07	5938.58
Nawabganj	81.55	80.98	7446.91	7429.28	80.36	81.59	7379.66	7432.57
Bhadpura	91.75	91.31	9174.59	9131.33	91.09	91.83	9109.28	9183.18
Bhuta	100.00	100.00	0.00	0.00	100.00	100.00	0.00	0.00
Faridpur								

Source: District Statistical Handbook, Bareilly district, Uttar Pradesh (1991-2016)

Figure 4: Inequality in operational hand holdings and area

The Gini value of 0.018 shows high inequality among the large and marginal landholders and the area operated by them because maximum marginal farmers have less land as compared to large landholders. Most of the time, maximum and small farmers mainly depend on agriculture. Hence, land fragmentation happened more in the marginal landholders than the larger landholders in which they operated the land. In addition, the population of the marginal landholder's family increases more than the larger landholder's family, creating a huge gap between the landholding and the area operated by them as compared to large farmers because they are also engaged in secondary and tertiary works for their livelihood. So their land is not divided as compared to marginal and small farmers.

The Gini value decreased to 0.003 in 2016 which shows nearly perfect equality between the land holding and the area operated. However, as the population increased, the land fragmentation rate also increased. The share of land holding and area operated was evenly distributed among the large and marginal landholders; the average land holding and area operated neutralises the gap between the large landholders and the marginal landholders. Due to the increasing population, the gap between the landholders decreases, creating less inequality between the shares of land holdings and the area operated by the landholders. As a result, larger landholdings are turning into small and marginal holdings whereas the marginal landholders became more marginalised by land fragmentation after they separated from the family.

Conclusion

Over time, significant inequalities have developed in the distribution of land holdings across the different sizes of landholding classes. The study shows that in the Bareilly district a large number of small and marginal farmers have very small land holdings and a small number of large farmers have large land holdings. It is often agreed that a value of more than 0.5 proves critical inequality in land holdings. The inequality increased (from 1991 to 2016) as the Gini value showed very less

inequality (0.018) in 1991. Still, the inequality decreased (0.003) in 2016 because the population in the marginal landholder's family increased more. When they separated, the fragmentation of land holding increased, providing less land to be operated. In the case of large landholders, the population was nearly stagnant and the land holding and area operated by them were also stagnant, creating a huge gap between the large and the marginal landholders and the area operated by them. Equality cannot be achieved until the uneven distribution of land and area operated will not evenly distributed among the different farmers.

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